

PEER-REVIEWED INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL

***Aarhat Multidisciplinary
International Education Research
Journal (AMIERJ)***

(Bi-Monthly)

Peer-Reviewed Journal

Impact factor:0.948

VOL - III

ISSUES - I

FEB-MAR

[2014]

**Chief-
Editor:**

**U b a l e
A m o l
B a b a n**

EFFECTIVE COMMUNICATION: A WAY TO SUCCESS

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“Communication is effective when the stimulus, as it was initiated and intended by the sender, corresponds by the receiver” -S.L. Tubbs and Sylvia Moss, in Human Communication

An effective communication is the key of sure success in the modern world of commerce. The increasing specialization and the expansion and complexity of today's trade fare have also brought about a revolution in the systems of communication. The businessman who wants to survive in the competition has to develop his communicating skills. He must know how to communicate with the help of new and speedy technical devices of communication. The efficient management be executives spend more than ninety per cent of their time in communication. Their efficiency depends upon their skills and effectiveness of communicating with others. He has to communicate with other traders and dealers for purchase and sell. He has to communicate with his superior in order to decide the objectives and directives. He has to communicate with his subordinates in order their get their cooperation and improve the productivity. He has to deal with banks, transport agencies, government official, legal advisors, insurances companies, experts, customers, etc. Therefore , it is very important for every businessman to know the art of how to communicate effectively.

Communication can be effective only if the receiver receives the message in the same form and context as is sent by the sender. When there is no mistake in interpretation and the sender gets the correct feedback, then communication can be termed as effective.

To compose effective oral and written messages, one must apply certain communication principles. These principles provides guidelines for choice of content and style of presentation, adapted to the purpose and the receiver of the message. To some extent, the principles overlap,

because they are based on a common concern for the audience, irrespective of whether that audience consists of listeners or readers.

The essentials of effective communication are:

- Positive and pleasant approach,
- Appropriate tone, pitch, quality, force and intensity of voice,
- Clarity of purpose and objective of communication,
- Clarity of thought and expression,
- Adequate knowledge of the communication receiver,
- Adequate knowledge of the subject,
- Objective and realistic approach,
- Self confidence and conviction,
- Organization of message,
- Proper selection and use of the media,
- Proper selection and use of the channel,
- Appropriate formality,
- Patience in listening,
- Adaptability,
- Attentiveness,
- 'You' attitude,
- Courtesy,
- Correctness,
- Completeness.

Positive and Pleasant Approach:

A positive and pleasant way of oral and written expression can easily build a goodwill in the customer-company relationship. Michael E. Adelstein says:

“It is not a matter of overstating or overselling, but of accentuating the positive, and minimising the negative. Every cloud may not have a silver lining, but there usually is some of hopeful or optimistic prospect in a business transaction.”

Appropriate Tone, Pitch, Quality, Force and Intensity of Voice:

A small child is always conscious of the fact that the voice he listens does not always say what the word mean. He often experiences this fact when he is remonstrated by his parents. He looks into the eyes of his daddy or mommy and judges what the tone of their voice means. The tone of voice gives an idea of depth and intensity of the emotions. Therefore, the communicator must strive to sound natural, friendly, sincere, and pleasant.

Clarity of purpose and objective of communication:

Communication is maintained at various levels of organizational hierarchy for the achievement of several objectives. A manager cannot plan, organize and control, if he does not communicate effectively to get information about the facts and circumstances relevant to his daily responsibilities. If he has to take correct decisions, the information received by him must be complete, correct, and concise. The administrator must be clear about the exact purpose behind his communication needs. The persuasive art is usually effective and successful as it suggestive and the appeal is indirect.

Clarity of thought and expression:

The cycle of communication starts at the origin of an idea in the mind of the communicator. It is the origin and source of the message to be communicated. The communicator must be clear about all the aspect of the idea in his mind and about the purpose for which it is to be communicated. When our objectives, thoughts and expression are clear and simple, the imparted message becomes easier to be understood by the receiver and the purpose of communication is effectively served.

Adequate knowledge of the communication receiver:

A communication receiver has a very important place in the communication cycle. When the receiver is absent, the communication situation itself cannot exist. Therefore, the message must be prepared by keeping in the view the type of person who is the receiver of it. The style, manner and content of the language must be carefully used to create goodwill in the mind of the receiver.

Adequate knowledge of the subject:

An adequate knowledge of the subject matter is the essential for effective communication through both oral and written media. Before writing a letter or delivering a speech, the communicator should thoroughly know the subject on which he is going to express his thoughts, ideas and feelings. An administrator, in a business firm, require the knowledge of why to communicate, what to communicate and how to communicate with different agencies, banks, etc. in order to be effective in his communication with them.

Objective and realistic approach:

The mental set, attitudes, opinions and prejudices of the receiver towards the sender and towards the organization have a marked effect on the meaning of the message. Adequate care should be taken by the sender that the information provided in the message does not mislead the receiver or hurt his feelings. A high level of trust and mutual respect between the sender and the receiver facilitates clear and objective communication.

Self confidence and conviction:

Lack of self-confidence can be a critical barrier to effective communication. A person must have the self confidence to communicate his achievements, his personal capabilities and his prospects. The communicator must build and develop in himself a justifiable self confidence.

Organization of message:

The organization of the message involves the selection of suitable media and composition of message by the systematic arrangement of symbols. The message must consist of an introduction, a body and a conclusion. The message can be organized in chronological pattern. A well organized message is always systematic and effective.

Proper selection and use of the Media:

A manager can communicate through a variety of media. The media available to him can be divided into four groups: i) audio-visual, ii) non-verbal, iii)oral, and iv) written.

All the communication media has their own advantages and disadvantages. Before selecting the media, it is essential to think over its relative suitability in communicating the message.

Proper selection and use of the Channel:

A communication channel runs along with the hierarchical line of authority in every organization. The employees have to follow these prescribed channels if they are to communicate with one another.

They are grouped in four divisions: i) upward, ii) downward, iii) vertical, and iv) horizontal, for effective communication.

Appropriate Formality:

In the organization, when the people work near each other and share each other's experiences, and problems, they are likely to *come* together for common purposes. When they come together, the informal group is formed. In order to coordinate and control such groups, the informal channel are more effective.

Patience in Listening:

If the receiver is a patience listener, with positive and flexible mind towards the speaker and understands the message by keeping himself mentally alert, the communication is bound to be effective.

Adaptability:

In human society and especially in our complex business world today, adaptability is an essential factor in effective communication with different people in different circumstances.

The adaptive responses of the receiver facilitates the incoming flow of the information at various levels in the organization.

Attentiveness:

The sender must be attentive enough in composing the message correctly, clearly,

precisely, and completely before transmitting it to the receiver. And the receiver must be attentive enough to listen and see every aspect of the message received by him.

‘You’ Attitude,

We must remember that the receiver is primarily in himself and in his gains. We can make our communication effective and persuasive by using the word ‘You’ as many times as possible and by trying to avoid the pronouns ‘I’ and ‘we’ in our message.

Courtesy:

Our personality is understood by the style and tone of our language and by our overall behavior. Our communication can be effective if we are courteous in our language and conduct. Courtesy can be defined as the considerate, friendly and sympathetic approach towards others.

Correctness:

The message should not contain any wrong information and should be authentic. Use the right level of languages or words. Check accuracy of figures, facts, and words. To make communication be effective it must be corrected.

Completeness:

The business message is complete it contains all the facts which the reader or listener needs for the reaction that the sender of the message so desires. To make communication effective it must to be provide all necessary information and give something extra , when desirable.

In crux we can say that to be effective business messages must be practical, providing the information that receiver need. Effective communication plans add value to organizations and often make the difference between success and failure of programs. ... Effective communication plans set the stage for managing the message, achieving results and Developing a project plan is the first stage in any project as the plan contains

critical and we can say that effective business communication is the back bone of any successful enterprise.

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